
ISSUES OF SOURCE AND ARTISTRY IN THE PRAISE CHAPTER OF
"SADDI ISKANDARI" EPIC

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Annotation: In the article, the chapter of praise in "Saddi Iskandarii" from the "Khamsa" epics, which occupies a special place in Alisher Navoi's work, is analyzed ideologically and artistically. During the analysis, attention will be paid to the sources of the ideas presented in the verses, that is, the Holy Qur'an, Hadith Sharif, aspects related to the teachings of Sufism. The poetic lines of the epic are described in prose and analyzed. While analyzing the chapter of Hamd, the formation of special traditions (traditional introductory chapters: basmala, hamd, munojot, na't) in the history of Uzbek literature is discussed.

Key words: Hamd, epic, artistic skill, talmeh, ratio, "Khamsa", "Saddi Iskandari".

Navoi also started "Saddi Iskandari", the last epic of "Khamsa", with praise of God. In this chapter, Navoi dwells on the history of the creation of the universe based on the teachings of Sufism: he gives a separate definition to each of the 9 layers of the sky, planets, and stars. He praises the greatness of the Creator. He emphasizes that the purpose of all this is to create the highest being - Adam. The poet builds the image of Alexander on the basis of the story of Zulqarnayn in the "Kahf" chapter of the Holy Qur'an. From the name of the epic "Saddi Iskandari" to the plot and composition of the work, this historical event is the basis. Alisher Navoi's saga differs from the works of his great predecessors, Nizami Ganjavi and Khusrav Dehlavi.

God, you are my God,

If someone is a shah, you can't pretend to be a liar.

God (God, address to God), godliness (ownership, mastery) belongs to you (approved without denial or opposition). If someone is a king, then you have the daab (habit, quality) of a gado. O Allah, you alone are the only owner of all the creatures on earth. This is an undeniable fact. Some people consider themselves to be a king despite being weak, but you are the owner of such greatness and unlimited power, but you have made a habit of being a king. The words of the verse (shah and gado) created the art of tazad. Holy Qur'an, Surah Luqman, verses 25-26: To Allah belong the heavens and the earth. Verily, Allah is the needy and praiseworthy. I swear that if they were asked: "Who created the heavens and the earth?" If you ask, of course, they

will say "Allah". You say "Praise be to God!" - say. No, most of them do not know (the truth).

God, you are so beautiful,
God bless you.

Khudovand (1. owner, master 2. governor, ruler) is a peerless monand (like). You are the lord (1. owner, master 2. ruler, ruler) of the lord (1. owner, master 2. ruler, ruler). Every quality of yours (address to Allah) is characteristic of rulers. You are very similar to them. But that alone falls short of your description. You are also the ruler of the rulers of the world. All governors obey you. Because you gave them such a great position.

You are the best,
The highs come and the lows are yours.

Powerful (1. high-handed, excellent 2. wrestlers) are yours (appeal to Allah) zerdast (subordinate, subordinate, dependent). All the great ones are low before you. All the nobles and nobles of the earth are under your command and obey you. All the heroes who think they are great are below you. You gave wrestling to wrestlers and greatness to the great. All of them are under your control. You are the ruler of the whole world. The words in the verse (high, low) created the art of tazad.

It's like a river of waves
There is an obvious place for you.

It's as if you have shown (1. gift, 2. generosity, open-handedness) to the waves (of appeal to Allah). You (appeal to Allah) made it clear that the house (1. workplace 2. maj: world) is a body (1. existence, existence 2. body, body). You (to Allah) have given a certain quality to everything that you have created. For example: You gave the river water the beauty of rippling, roaring, hissing flow. And you (address to Allah) revealed the existence of the world to everyone. Your zeal is endless. You created each creature for a specific purpose.

You know how many people in the world,
Come and know that I am very good.

Creature (1. existence, existence 2. body, body) of people with kom (desire, desire, purpose) with jud (1. gift, gift 2. generosity, openness of hand). Come and have a good (1. gift, 2. generosity, open-handedness) good (1. existence, existence 2. body, body). All the wishes and desires of the people of existence (total beings on earth) have come true because of your gifts. You gave them what they wanted from you. Such generosity and open-handedness is only suitable for your body, it is only possible for you.

Whenever your body does it, I will eat it.
All things are human beings.

When existence (1. existence, existence 2. body, body) becomes visible (appearance, appearance) food (antiquity), all things are existence (1. existence, existence 2. body, body) and man (no, absence) will be. When your (address to Allah) body appears, all existing things will flow into the world of non-existence. Until now, no one has been able to see your beauty. Because no creature can do that. You are the only one who sees and knows.

Kavnain of the time was madum,

Adam had a letter in his mouth.

The time of Kavnain (two worlds: that world, this world) was madum (nothingness). Adam (no, absence) was a letter (hidden, kept secret) in tangnoy (1. narrow road 2. throat, larynx). Nothing existed on earth. That world (eternal, eternal world) and this world (the world we live in now) did not exist either. These two worlds were hidden and hidden in the narrow corridor of the world of nothingness. There was no sign of life.

What day did you have an anniversary?

Ne night tour and anbarfishon.

Which day oraz (face, face) had a mark (mark, mark). Which night turra (kokil, braided hair, curly hair) and there was anbarfishon (fragrance, anbar spreader). There was no sign of the bright face of the day on the earth, nor of the night's barn-scattering owls. It was all abstract. At distich (day, night) words formed the art of tazad.

The hall of Sahardin is not clean.

Shafaqdin doesn't have a smile on his face.

From dawn (the place where the rooster crows during the day), the sky hall (maj: sky, sky) ro' (face, face) is not clean. From Shafaq (the redness that appears in the blue during sunset) there is no aning goza (a red substance applied to the face, elik) on the face. Since dawn, the sky is not clear, that is, there are dark clouds floating in the sky. The redness that appears at sunset did not redden the face of the sky.

Neither the sky, nor the continuous moment,

Neither el, nor el javr of his era.

Neither aflok (sky, sky) nor muttasil (consecutive, continuous) and period (1. circle, teverak 2. time, time 3. layer). From the time of ne el a, elga javr (suffering, oppression, oppression). This sky and the stars have seen how many times have passed continuously. During these times, he lived for many years and endured various oppressions.

What do you want from the world?

What is happening is ready to eat.

There were traces (marks, symbols) from Ne Olam Dayor (1. country, country 2. house, place). Ne dayar (1. country, country 2. house, space) had dayyars (residents). Initially, there were no targets from any country on earth. There were no countries and no people living in it. You (appeal to Allah) wanted all of these things to exist, and you made it happen.

You were a kind of existence, honey existence

That was not enough.

You (appeal to Allah) existed as a species, but (perhaps) a body (1. existence, existence 2. body, body). That there was no nangi nabud (name of non-existence) for your bud (existence, existence). You (address to Allah) already existed, maybe you have a body. Your existence has never had the name of absence. That is, no one can deny your existence. We don't need to see you with our eyes to know that you exist.

The commandment of love is not hidden

That it is impossible to fall in love.

The commandment of love is not hidden. That it is impossible not to fall in love. The desire to be equally loved by everyone is not hidden from anyone. Because there is no way not to fall in love with your (appeal to Allah). Every created being is your lover.

It doesn't matter if I understand closely, man.

You are in love with your lover.

If I understand closely, there is a non-existent person. You are love, you are in love, you are the lover. Allah is also addressed in this verse. If you look closely, there is another world of nothingness. That place is the place of God. No other breed lives there. You (appeal to Allah) are love, lover, and lover. This very verse is a logical continuation of the stanza above. It is Allah alone who falls in love with a lover, creates love, and becomes a lover.

That's it, my love, you're dead

I love you so much.

Both the beloved and the lover are you. Greetings to you (address to Allah) ishq, ushshaq (lovers, lovers) (this Arabic word is often placed at the end of letters and other writings and means that this is all, that's all, that's the end). Navoi ends the last verse of "Saddi Iskandari" by addressing God. In the meantime, you are the one who is the lover and the one who is in love with the lover. ate.

There is an inextricable connection between the attributes of God, the owner of infinite intelligence, and the fact that Alexander, the main character of the work, manages military campaigns and the country with intelligence.

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